

LUNAR SURFACE DATING WITH CRATERSTATS-III: INSTANT WORKSHOP. Greg Michael, Center for Lunar and Planetary Sciences, CAS Institute of Geochemistry, Guiyang, 550002, China.
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Introduction: *Craterstats* is a software tool to analyse and plot crater count data for lunar and planetary surface dating. It has evolved through several iterations since 2007, and the current one, *Craterstats-III*, was developed in 2021 with the support of the US Geological Survey with the intention to make it available as a long term resource for planetary scientists, independent of proprietary software.

The latest version (3.3.2) includes two new analyses: (1) a visualization of the relationship between measurement area and the expected measurement uncertainty as a function of actual surface age, and (2) a sequence plot output for comparing sets of related age measurements. There has also been a recent focus on making the software more convenient and efficient to use.

This poster will provide a quick introduction to the tool, both for new users and for people working with its predecessor, *Craterstats-II*, outlining some of the changes in usage and improvements in output.

Crater counts: The raw data for a crater dating analysis is a list of measured crater diameters together with the area they were counted on. Some analyses also need a digitization of the count area boundary and a measure of the boundary perimeter. *OpenCraterTools* [1] covers all these requirements in QGIS, but data from other sources can also be used.

Usage: *Craterstats-III* is a command-line program. The simplest command is just to plot some data

A model age estimate is added by providing a diameter range and the calculation type (Poisson, buffered-Poisson, differential-fit, cumulative-fit) –

Alternative data presentations, e.g. cumulative, Hartmann, or R-plot, as well as other chronology systems may be specified –

An analysis is typically constructed in an incremental fashion, as the steps above show. This may include the addition of further datasets or extra diameter ranges. Upon generating each plot, the software also produces a file containing the options used –

```
areal.cs
-pr cumul
-cs Yue22
-p source=areal.diam
-p type=poisson,range=[.15,1.]
```

and it generally becomes more convenient to refine the plot by modifying this file for all but the simplest

cases. For example, the Trask (1966) equilibrium function and Wilhelms (1987) epoch curves could be added as follows –

```

                                areal1.cs
- pr cumul
- cs Yue22
- ef Trask
- ep Wilhelms
- p source=areal.diam
- p type=poisson,range=[.15,1.]

```

An updated plot image can then be generated with the simpler command, using this as an input file –

New analyses include a visualization of the relationship between measurement area and the expected measurement uncertainty as a function of actual surface age [2] –

and the possibility to show multiple age measurements in a single figure to visualize the sequence history (as a violin plot for Poisson evaluation or bar plot for fitting methods) –

sequence.cs

```

- pr sequence
- ep Wilhelms
- xrange 4 1
- legend Af
- p src=e1.scc,range=[0.24,1.5],type=poisson
- p src=e2.scc,range=[0.25,1.5]
- p src=e3.scc,range=[0.25,1.5]
...further similar lines omitted...

```


Summary: *Craterstats-III* is designed to replicate the output of the previous version as closely as possible. It produces plots in cumulative, differential, Hartmann, and R-plot styles [3] with possible overlays of crater counts, isochrons, equilibrium functions and epoch boundaries, as well as chronology and impact rate functions and new uncertainty and sequence plots. Data can be shown with various binnings or unbinned, and age estimates made by either cumulative fitting, differential fitting, or Poisson evaluation. Numerical results can be output as text for further processing elsewhere, and with formatting for Word or Latex documents (e.g. $\mu 1.75^{+0.057}_{-0.055}$ Ga). Most published chronology systems are already set up for use, but new ones may be added by the user. For a recent review of the state of the art in lunar cratering chronology, see [4].

The software can be found together with installation instructions for different operating systems, usage instructions and source code at:

<https://github.com/ggmichael/craterstats>

I invite you to contact me if assistance is needed.

References:

[1] Heyer T. et al. (2023) *Planet. Space Sci.* **231**, 105687.
 [2] Michael G. and Liu J. (2025) *Icarus* **431**, 116489.
 [3] Arvidson R. E. et al. (1979) *Icarus* **37**, 467–474.
 [4] Hiesinger H. et al. (2023) *Rev. Mineral. Geochem.* **89**, 401–451.